

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

Deliverable D2.3

Integration of new cohort infrastructures to the ELIXIR AAI

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1. Executive Summary

In the previously carried out work in CINECA WP2, described in the deliverable D2.1¹, the ELIXIR AAI has been integrated with the CanDIG AAI to enable interoperability between the two infrastructures. After that, the primary focus has evolved towards supporting standardized authorization solutions, namely by implementing and using the GA4GH Passports and Visas² standard in the bridged AAI solution. With the implementation finished, the work plan has shifted towards integrating more cohort infrastructures into the bridged AAI resulting in a wider set of use cases and wider cooperation possibilities, together with more functionality provided to the users and an extensive set of services integrated with the AAI environment.

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the work carried out has contributed to the following objectives:

- a) To provide AAI services to enable federated cohort data discovery (WP1), analysis (WP4), and clinical applications
- b) To upgrade ELIXIR and Canada AAI to support GA4GH protocols to ensure CINECA interoperability with other global cohort infrastructures.
- c) To provide assistance and expertise to enable organisations in Europe, Canada, and Africa to access AAI services.

3. Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

ELIXIR AAI and its migration into Life Science AAI

ELIXIR AAI³ was a service through which researchers have been authenticated and gained access to the services of different ELIXIR nodes. With one user name and Single Sign-On, researchers could access all ELIXIR services granted to them. The ELIXIR AAI service was produced by the ELIXIR nodes in Finland and the Czech Republic. It has been a successful European-wide authentication solution, which has been connected to secure data sharing.

The ELIXIR AAI was migrated to Life Science AAI (LS Login)⁴ service in April 2022⁵. This step has been a logical evolution when ELIXIR joined its effort with 12 other research infrastructures operating in the field of Life Sciences. The primary motivation has been to enable unified access via a common infrastructure to the services provided by these RIs, while also taking into account the possibility to share user bases and considering the economic side of operating AAI as well.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/3938916>

² https://github.com/ga4gh-duri/ga4gh-duri.github.io/blob/master/researcher_ids/ga4gh_passport_v1.md

³ <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/compute/aai>

⁴ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/>

⁵ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/news-and-links/elixir-migration-news.html>

Controlled access to data leveraging the GA4GH Passports and Visas standard

While building on the concepts and functionality available in the ELIXIR AAI, Life Science AAI has also adopted the model of controlled access to sensitive data sets. The most sensitive services, such as access to genomics data, often require presenting a research plan to a Data Access Committee (DAC). The DAC then carries a decision of granting or rejecting the access, which is recorded in systems able to expose these decisions to other systems, e.g. via API endpoints.

Life Science AAI integrates with repositories of these controlled access grants (e.g. the European Genome-phenome Archive - EGA). By querying users' data access permissions from such repositories, it assembles them into a standardized representation covered by the GA4GH Passports and Visas⁶ standard. The Life Science AAI is therefore acting as a broker, assembling the GA4GH Passport from the Visas coming from the resources and enriching the list with self-created visas based on the data stored in the LS AAI itself (affiliations and roles, accepted terms and policies, linked identities, researcher status) and releasing the GA4GH Passport to downstream Passport consumers. The REMS software (Resource Entitlement Management System) supporting the data access request process is also integrated into Life Science AAI in several instances acting as the mentioned permissions repository. The process of releasing a GA4GH Passport and Visas is illustrated by the following diagram.

With the evolution of the GA4GH Passports and Visas standard⁷, the LS AAI implemented a pilot version of the proposed update to the specification (v1.2). After approving the proposed standard, the pilot implementation has been finalized into a production-grade implementation and made available to the services making use of the standard. The updated specification gives an alternative way of representing the GA4GH Passport as a JWT token containing the GA4GH passport visas.

⁶ https://github.com/ga4gh-duri/ga4gh-duri.github.io/blob/master/researcher_ids/ga4gh_passport_v1.md

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User Scenarios

For this deliverable we have identified the following user scenarios:

- controlled access to a biobanking environment facilitated using the BBMRI Negotiator service
- controlled access control genomics data in the European Genomics Data Infrastructure (GDI)
- integration of the European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (EJP-RD) into the Life Science AAI
- integration of the European Federation for Cancer Images (EUCAIM) into the Life Science AAI

3.2 Description of Work

User flows

Controlled access to a biobanking environment facilitated using the BBMRI Negotiator service

BBMRI-ERIC⁸ is a European research infrastructure for biobanking. It brings together all the main players from the biobanking field – researchers, biobankers, industry, and patients – to boost biomedical research. The BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator⁹ is a Service that provides an efficient communication platform for biobankers and researchers requesting samples and/or data.

It substantially simplifies the communication steps that are necessary to obtain information on the availability of relevant samples/data, particularly if the researchers need to communicate with multiple candidate biobanks.

In this flow the user uses the BBMRI Negotiator Service to negotiate access to clinical material stored by biobanks. The process starts with the requester (researcher) logging into the Negotiator service. After successfully logging in, the researcher performs a query to discover the relevant results of interest for the researcher. The negotiation process starts when the researcher fills in the form and applies for access to the sensitive material. Following is the review of the application by representative persons of the target biobanks, granting or rejecting access and negotiating the access conditions.

Controlled access control genomics data in the European Genomics Data Infrastructure (GDI)

The GDI¹⁰ infrastructure aims to provide a European-wide infrastructure for sharing and computing using the genomics data. It builds on the foundations laid by the 1MG and B1MG projects. The user process starts by discovering the relevant databy executing a search query, followed by submitting an application for data access if needed, requesting possibly transnational transfer of the relevant data into a Secure Processing Environment (SPE), executing a computational workflow and extracting the results from the environment.

Integration of the European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (EJP-RD) into the Life Science AAI

The European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (EJP RD)¹¹ is a programme aiming to create an effective rare diseases research ecosystem for progress, innovation and for the benefit of everyone

⁸<https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/>

⁹<https://negotiator.bbmri-eric.eu/login.xhtml>

¹⁰<https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

¹¹<https://www.ejprarediseases.org/>

with a rare disease. This year, it will build a Virtual Platform, aiming to open a single door to discover, query and eventually access patient registries, biobanks, genomics & multi-omics repositories, knowledge bases, resources (such as animal models and cell lines libraries), omics deposition & analysis platforms, and translational & clinical research supporting material and services, in a coordinated manner. The primary user flow is to execute a federated query using the centralized discovery portal, with an optional login enabling more in-detail discovery of the relevant resources.

Integration of the European Federation for Cancer Images (EUCAIM) into the Life Science AAI

EUCAIM¹² targets clinicians, researchers and innovators, providing the means to finally build validated clinical decision-making systems supporting diagnosis, treatment and predictive medicine to benefit citizens. Its plan for this year is to implement a federation of providers compliant with this legal ground, defining common data models, ontologies, quality standards, FAIR principles and de-identification procedures. EUCAIM will provide a comprehensive dashboard for data discovery, federated search, metadata harvesting, annotation and distributed processing, including federated and privacy-preserving learning. EUCAIM will build a central hub to host the Atlas of Cancer Images, enabling the development of trustworthy AI tools. The workflow from the user perspective is similar to the one described in the GDI - to cover the whole process of discovering the data, data access control, computation on the data and finishing by the publication of the results.

Technical Solution

All of the below-described solutions are taking into account the previously done integration of ELIXIR AAI and CanDIG AAI by bridging these two infrastructures and providing the ability to cross login of their users. The solution has been transferred together with the migration of the ELIXIR AAI into the LS AAI.

Controlled access to a biobanking environment facilitated using the BBMRI Negotiator service

The solution in this user flow lies in integrating the Negotiator service with the Life Science AAI for leveraging its authentication and authorization capabilities. Primarily, it enables a unified login via LS AAI using the users' LS ID, while providing the Negotiator with information about the researcher status of the user and records of what resources is the user able to manage in the application. This information is recorded in the Perun system which serves as an Identity Management part of the LS AAI.

In addition, the LS AAI facilitates the application system for gaining the status of "representing" a resource by utilizing the registrations into organizational units managed in the IDM system. Such applications are reviewed by authoritative persons coming from the biobanks, national nodes, and biobanks networks, or are carried out by the management staff of BBMRI or the people already granted the representative role for a resource. The BBMRI Negotiator workflow is also illustrated by the following picture.

¹²<https://www.eibir.org/projects/eucaim/>

Controlled access control genomics data in the European Genomics Data Infrastructure (GDI)

This project started with the goal of providing a so-called Starter-kit representing a reference implementation of the infrastructure needed to be deployed in each of the participating nodes. Life Science AAI is a key component of the whole infrastructure, covering the aspects of logging into relevant systems and heavily utilizing the integration with permission repositories (e.g. REMS) and the ability to translate such authorization information into the GA4GH Passport concept. It also relies on the ability to provide the GA4GH Passports and Visas to other components of the infrastructure, like discovery components (Beacon), computational tools (Task and Workflow execution services - TES, WES), or the authentication capabilities for logging into centralized and node level portals.

Integration of the European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (EJP-RD) into the Life Science AAI

Integration with the EJP-RD Virtual Platform is done on two levels. The first one is the integration of a centralized Virtual Platform Portal with the Life Science AAI using its authentication via the OIDC interface. The portal is primarily open for anyone, with the idea of optional login enabling further capabilities of the portal. An example might be the potentially wider result set of the discovered resources when executing the discovery query as an authenticated user. The second level of integration is the connection of LS AAI and particular resources that utilize the provided functionality for local authentication and roles management.

Integration of the European Federation for Cancer Images (EUCAIM) into the Life Science AAI

The EUCAIM project developed an infrastructure, which has been connected to the Life Science AAI acting as one of the alternatives for logging into the environment. A further integration on the level of transferring the roles management and access management from a local Keycloak instance into the Life Science AAI has been planned.

3.3 Next steps

A primary focus will be put on three areas of work. The first area will be looking for new infrastructures that could be integrated into the LS AAI environment, extending the environment of the bridged AAI solutions and providing access to even more resources. This activity will contribute primarily to more services being available for the users who are already using the infrastructure, as well as extending the user base for whom these services will be offered. The second activity will be a more extensive integration with the infrastructures and continuous improvement of integration to transfer more functionality into the LS AAI and let infrastructures focus more on the provided functionality and cover more use cases without the need to deeply care about the authentication and authorization process. By exploring new methods and transferring more authorization into the AAI environment, services will be able to simply define and re-use the defined authorization rules in the AAI itself instead of implementing it on their side. The third area is the continuous improvement of the AAI service, e.g. by implementing the drafted Multi-Factor Authentication, enabling alternative sources of authentication (e-wallets, industry partners, ...), and the general evolution of the AAI service, e.g. by early adoption and feeding back on the evolution of GA4GH standards.

4. References

Documentation:

- [GA4GH support in LS AAI](#)

Tool:

- [Life Science AAI Identity Management](#)
- [Life Science AAI User Profile](#)
- [GA4GH Passport tester](#)
- [BBMRI-ERIC Negotiator](#)

Standard

- [GA4GH Passports and Visas standard](#)

Projects, organizations

- [BBMRI-ERIC](#)
- [Genomics Data Infrastructure](#)
- [European Joint Project on Rare Diseases](#)
- [European Federation for Cancer Images](#)

5. Abbreviations

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
BBMRI	Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure

DAC	Data Access Committee
EGA	European Genome-phenome Archive
EJP-RD	The European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases
EUCAIM	European Federation for Cancer Images
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GDI	European Genomics Data Infrastructure
IDM	Identity Management system
IdP	Identity Provider
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JWT	JSON Web Token
LS AAI	Life Science AAI service, also called LS Login
OIDC	OpenID Connect
REMS	Resource Entitlement Management System
SAML2	Security Assertion Markup Language version 2
SPE	Secure Processing Environment
TES	Task Execution Service
WES	Workflow Execution Service

6. Delivery and schedule

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7. Adjustments made

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8. Appendices

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